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Beyond the Applause

Each year the spotlight brightly gleams,
On teachers who fulfill their dreams.
With plaques and praises held up high,
Their names are echoed to the sky.

Yet when the cheers begin to fade,
And silent halls replace the parade,
What keeps their passion burning bright,
And guides their steps through every night?

It is the heart that seeks to learn,
A steady flame that will not turn.
Through graduate studies, research, and more,
They open yet another door.

For teaching is not merely a task,
Nor a role defined by what awards may ask.
It is a calling deeply known,
A seed of purpose carefully sown.

With humble hearts and grateful minds,
They leave no struggling child behind.
Their honesty and hope inspire,
And lift young dreams a little higher.

They document each gain and fall,
Reflecting deeply through it all.
For every lesson, every plan,
Helps shape a better, wiser hand.

They do not journey on their own,
Nor work in classrooms all alone.
With parents, leaders, friends, and peers,
They build strong bridges through the years.

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Yet even heroes face their test,
Heavy workloads and little rest.
Limited resources, pressures too,
Can challenge all they strive to do.

And so the truth becomes quite clear:
Excellence grows when support is near.
Schools must nurture, guide, and care,
Creating spaces strong and fair.

Like a house built firm and tall,
Each pillar matters, one and all.
Growth, support, and partnership blend,
To help great teachers still ascend.

So let us look beyond the prize,
Beyond the applause and admiring eyes.
For the greatest honor we can give
Is helping dedicated teachers thrive and live.

Behind each learner's success each day,
A teacher quietly lights the way.
Still growing, serving, reaching new heights
A beacon of hope, a guiding light.